

A SYSTEM OF INDICATORS AND A METHOD OF ANALYSIS REPRESENTING THE DEMAND AND SUPPLY FOR THE COMPANY'S PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

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Abstract:

Annotation: Complex marketing analysis is the main part of the marketing research system, effective marketing conclusions are made by collecting sources, registering them, processing information related to goods, work and services on the market. As an object of comprehensive economic analysis in the process of marketing research, in our opinion, firstly, the real market process together with consumers and competitors, and secondly, the specific economic and production capabilities of the enterprise in the production of product types should be taken into account.

Keyword: marketing, optimal assortment program, company's products.

Every enterprise, firm and organization operating in our republic should study the market and operate according to the principle of "what kind of product should be produced, for whom should be produced and how much should be produced", highly qualified specialists are required. In his writings, the President touched upon this issue and said, "Looking for large and small projects for technical and technological renewal of production in order to ensure product competitiveness, finding the necessary funds and resources for this is the first priority of every enterprise manager and engineer technical staff. should have an important task and obligation". Based on the information collected by these specialists, the enterprise should analyze the market situation in depth in order to effectively use resources and meet the needs of consumers. For this purpose, complex marketing research is conducted. Through marketing, new types of services are constantly offered, which, due to the

expansion of their market, the company achieves a high level of profit. Business activities are regulated through marketing . Therefore, the analysis of the result of the production activity of the enterprise should begin with the analysis of the marketing activity.

Through a deep study of both interrelated objects, an optimal assortment program is created, taking into account the market situation and the company's capabilities. By implementing this program, the competitiveness and stability of the company's products will be ensured. The main tasks of complex marketing analysis :

- assessment, analysis of the demand and need for enterprise services, making sure that the production program has a real basis;
- analysis of the main factors affecting the requirements for products and services;
- to determine the types of services that are not provided ;
- evaluation policy and analysis of assortment types;
- evaluation and analysis of product competitiveness;

The information system of comprehensive marketing analysis consists of internal source, external source, marketing research. In the process of analysis, each of these departments participates as an independent information system. Internal information sources include operational and current production and scientific and technical sources of accounting and statistical reports of the enterprise. The system of external resources includes the external activities of the enterprise, the market and its infrastructure, the situation of buyers and suppliers of goods, the actions of competitors, measures taken by the state to regulate the market mechanism, etc. These sources are reflected in periodic and special publications, statistical collections, reviews of research conducted by commercial organizations. The list of such sources is supplemented by the sources of the organized exhibition and conference, the meeting of businessmen and the minutes of their negotiations. The business plan (marketing plan) of the enterprise is also used as the information source of the analysis.

Marketing includes business activities related to market research, planning product assortment according to consumer orders, market capture, advertising, and delivery of goods and services from producer to consumer.

In the conditions of market relations, management of the enterprise makes marketing the basis of production, because the basis of making business decisions is not production possibilities, but market requirements, customer needs. As a result, the scale of the enterprise, the structure of organizational management of the enterprise, principles and methods of management, and directions of service are determined by the market. The market consists of supply and demand.

Demand is, first of all, the manifestation of the need for any goods or services in the market and their provision in monetary terms.

Supply is defined as the mass of goods that are on the market at a given time or that can be delivered to it.

Demand arises primarily as a demand for resources and consumer goods, commoditized services, the first aimed at meeting production consumption, and the second at personal consumption.

As the human society develops, the need and demand of mankind for goods and material values continuously changes and increases in the conditions where the progress of science and technology is updated with rapid steps.

Analysis of the complex marketing system of the enterprise

There is a change (elasticity) of demand, which is:

- price change and status;
- the number of customers and their tastes and desires;
- consumer purchasing ability;
- possibility of inflation, etc.

Among the factors that determine the above demand, the price of goods and the purchasing power of consumers occupy an important place. Supply may remain constant after the market is fully supplied, in which case there is no need to increase the supply as the price rises. Then the volume of production will not change, and the supply will be stabilized independent of the price.

The variability of supply, like the variability of demand in general, changes in the price of a commodity, the index of variability of supply (K) is used to determine the degree of change in supply. According to him,

$$K = \frac{\text{Change in quantity of ordered goods (\%)}}{\text{Grades Change(\%)}}$$

- If, $K > 1$, the offer is variable;
 Inversion if $K = 1$;
 If $K < 1$ it is absolutely invariant.

Sales volume, average price level, sales revenue and profit depend on domestic and foreign market.

A correct, clear strategy is developed by studying the company's product into groups. Through the implementation of the strategy, the ways to bring them to the "milk cows" and "star" categories will be determined by financing the goods belonging to the "heavy child" category.

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